

YOUTH POLICY AND THE NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY: LEGAL FOUNDATIONS, SOCIAL INNOVATIONS, AND GLOBAL EXPERIENCE

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the scientific and theoretical foundations of state youth policy, its development strategy, and its role in modern society. The content, objectives, and legal-regulatory framework of youth policy are examined on the basis of a scientific approach. Through the analysis of foreign experience, appropriate solutions to emerging challenges are proposed. At the same time, the article highlights the distinctive features observed in the implementation of youth policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan, including its harmony with national values and the activities of practical programs oriented toward the social sphere.

Main part

Approaching the younger generation as a driving force that ensures societal development has created conditions for the formation of state youth policy in various countries. In this process, the United Nations has played a significant role. During the 1960s–1980s of the twentieth century, a number of documents defining new principles of attitudes toward youth were adopted by the UN. With the proclamation in 1965 of the UN General Assembly's Declaration on the Promotion among Youth of the Ideals of Peace, Mutual Respect and Understanding between Peoples, youth social issues became a priority focus of the organization.

Within the framework of UNESCO, more than one hundred documents related to youth issues were adopted. It was precisely on UNESCO's initiative that the World Congress on Youth Affairs began its activities in 1985, and the same year was proclaimed by the UN as the International Youth Year.

In accordance with the resolution of the UN General Assembly of 14 December 1995, a World Programme of Action for Youth to the Year 2000 and Beyond was adopted. Subsequently, by Resolution No. 54/120 of 20 January 2000, the Lisbon Declaration on Youth Policies and Programmes, adopted at the World Conference of Ministers Responsible for Youth held in Lisbon in 1998, was approved¹.

¹ Молодежь в Организации Объединенных Наций / Библиотека документов ООН, связанных с молодежью. [Электронный ресурс]. - Режим доступа: <http://www.un.org/youth.html>

These documents continue to serve to legally reinforce, at both the international and national levels, the implementation of the main objective of youth policy, which is to ensure the active participation of young people and youth organizations in social life².

The vertical, horizontal, cross-sectoral, and interdisciplinary approaches to the implementation of state youth policy are approaches that ensure interaction and interconnection among authorities at various levels, systems, sectors, academic disciplines, and social institutions. Such a multifaceted approach is of great importance for the effective implementation of youth policy.

The vertical approach (theory) refers to the implementation of state policy in a coordinated manner across different levels of governance, from the central level to the local level. Within this approach, close interaction between the higher (national) level of state authority and local levels (regional, district, city, village) plays a crucial role. For example, a youth policy strategy defined at the national level is adapted to local conditions and implemented on the ground.

The horizontal approach (theory) reflects cooperation among state authorities, non-governmental organizations, civil society institutions, and representatives of the private sector. Within this framework, various agencies—such as those responsible for education, healthcare, employment, culture, sports, and other sectors—coordinate their activities. This makes it possible to address youth-related problems comprehensively and holistically.

The cross-sectoral approach (theory) implies the integration and interaction of various economic, social, and political sectors in the implementation of youth policy. Based on this approach, the capacities of education, healthcare, employment, crime prevention, ecology, information technologies, and other sectors are combined. As a result, youth-related issues are addressed not within a single sector, but through broad-based cooperation.

The interdisciplinary approach (theory) means the comprehensive use of knowledge and methods from various academic disciplines—such as sociology, pedagogy, psychology, law, economics, political science, and others—in the scientific development and implementation of youth policy. Through this approach, the needs, problems, and social behavior of young people are analyzed in depth, and scientifically grounded strategies and programs are developed. Naturally, each theory has its own role and foundation, and their combination is considered the most effective and beneficial for youth.

Youth issues constitute one of the most important priority areas of state policy pursued in our country. Based on the “Uzbek model” of development, the principles and mechanisms of state youth policy have been developed, and its legal framework has been established.

Indeed, in any progressive state, youth policy is considered a priority. State youth policy refers to a system of measures implemented by the state to create favorable conditions and opportunities for the free socialization of young people and their effective self-realization in the interests of the country. In essence, this policy aims to ensure state development, enhance future competitiveness, and strengthen national security.

² Лиссабонская декларация по молодежной политике и Брагский план действий в интересах молодежи (A/53/378) / Библиотека документов ООН, связанных с молодежью. [Электронный ресурс]. - Режим доступа: <http://www.un.org/youth.html>

State youth policy is, first and foremost, an element of a country's internal policy and serves to purposefully regulate relations between youth and the state.

In our country as well, youth policy is one of the priority directions of state activity, and its main goal is to create socio-economic, legal, and organizational conditions for the social formation and development of young people. As noted by Krinsky, youth should be understood as a socio-demographic group that differs from others by specific age characteristics, social status, and its role as an active subject of the social system, culture, and socialization, determined on the basis of contemporary age boundaries³. In this definition, the term “youth” refers to individuals belonging to a specific age group defined within a social, cultural, and demographic context. This group differs from others due to its age-specific characteristics and occupies a distinct position within the social system.

Young people are active subjects in the process of socialization, through which they form both personal and collective identities. This process is carried out through cultural and social norms. Moreover, the concept of “modern age boundaries” implies that youth are defined not only biologically, but also within social and cultural contexts that establish certain boundaries for this group.

For example, in contemporary society, young people have a new and more complex social role compared to past perceptions. They are not merely members of an age group, but also active participants in implementing social change within society. Thus, this definition views youth as an important part of society and emphasizes their interactions and their place within the social system.

According to sociologist Muhammad Tagi Sheikh, in every society youth represent the most unified, influential, and at the same time influenceable group. He also emphasizes that targeted investment in education, science, and moral development plays an effective role in the growth and dynamism of young people⁴. In other words, investing in these areas enhances young people's knowledge and skills and creates opportunities for their active participation in social, economic, and cultural life. Youth represent the future of society, and their educational and moral development has a direct impact on overall social progress. Therefore, creating the necessary conditions for the effective development of young people is of great importance for the well-being of society.

Today, the active participation of young people is especially important in the process of shaping youth policy. International experience in the field of state youth policy shows that involving young people—particularly representatives of non-governmental organizations and the private sector—in defining youth policy priorities and in making socio-political decisions serves as a key factor for success. This is because young people themselves best understand and recognize the needs and interests of their peers⁵. Today, the study of youth-related issues from the perspective of youth policy is comprehensive in nature. Before examining the specific features of state youth policy in modern Uzbekistan, it is necessary to clearly define the conceptual framework related to this topic. For this purpose, concepts such as “youth policy,”

³ Кирницкий В.В. Проблема формирования патриотических ценностей в массовом сознании российской молодежи: диссертация... кандидата философских наук. - Москва, 2016 – 176 с

⁴ Mohammad Taghi Sheykhi. *Sociology of Youth*, 29 July 2021, Page 1-110

⁵ Finn Yrjar Denstad. *Youth Policy Manual*. Council of Europe Publishing. September 2009. p.53.

“models of youth policy,” “principles of youth policy,” as well as “the object and subject of youth policy,” and other related notions should be precisely defined. In addition, special attention should be paid to the analysis of political science methods applied in the study of state youth policy.

As a system of specific principles, approaches, and methods, the methodology of any science constitutes the foundation of its field of research. Political science methodology refers to a distinct field that examines the history, essence, meaning, role, and significance of the methods and approaches applied within this discipline. Based on the general methodology of studying youth policy, it becomes necessary to refer to political categories such as state policy, social policy, and state youth policy.

Indeed, the analysis of these categories makes it possible to clearly identify and understand all the elements of the concept of state youth policy⁶. From the time when the concept of youth policy became the priority of the official activities of public policy, this concept began to institutionalize in the social humanities.

Since the beginning of the 90s of the last century, interpretations of this concept in a broad, narrow and institutional sense have been discussed, which have not lost their relevance to this day⁷. The fact that youth policy has not lost importance to this day suggests that the concept is expanding year by year, as well as playing an important role at the level of the state and society. The policy is aimed at social justice, equality, opportunity creation and active participation of young people in society, and its interpretations are broad, narrow and institutional, that is, they also occupy an important place in the form of international legal acts and regulatory acts adopted by many states. For example, documents such as the UN Youth Declaration or the EU youth policy are being implemented in the manner of appearances. The universal interpretation of youth policy is also reflected in official UN documents on youth. In these documents, the concept of youth policy is described somewhat broadly: in particular, it is reflected that “an integral part of the state's activities aimed at the comprehensive development of youth is the calculation of youth policy”⁸. Youth policy covers not only public organizations, but also parties, social movements, civil society institutions and other types of social institutions that also focus on youth issues within their overall activities.

President Of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev noted, “the upbringing of the younger generation has become important and relevant in all times. But in the 21st century in which we live, this issue is really becoming a matter of life-matter”. It is not for nothing that our country President stressed that youth policy will become one of the priorities of the country during the first years of his career as president of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The firmness of the youth life position is important for the sustainable perspective and development of the whole people and society. It has also been noted in the socio-political literature, stating that “the greatness of a nation lies in how much it has realized its national identity, its political maturity, its national”⁹.

⁶ Меркулов П. А. Методология изучения государственной молодежной политики — приглашение к дискуссии // Вестник Ассоциации ВУЗов туризма и сервиса. 2012. № 4(23). С. 79–82.

⁷ Н.Жўраев. Янгиланиш концепцияси: яратилиши, эволюцияси ва амалиёти. – Т.: Маънавият, 2002. – Б. 43

⁸ Молодежь в организации Объединенных Наций / Библиотека документов ООН, связанных с молодежью. [Электронный ресурс]. - Режим доступа: <http://www.un.org/youth.html>.

⁹ Раҳмонов Р., Ғофуров З. Мустақиллик ва миллий ўзликни англашнинг тикланиши. Тошкент: Ўзбекистон, 1999. –Б. 20.

Historically, focusing on youth politics, one person lived in Ancient Rome for an average of 27 years. In England in the first half of the 19th century, a 12-year-old child was practically considered an adult: the labor legislation applied to him was equated to older individuals. At the end of the XIX century, the average life expectancy in Russia was only 48 years¹⁰.

In turn, in the early years of our independence, the State Youth Policy maintained its relevance, on November 20, 1991, the law “on the basics of State Youth Policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted by the Republic of Uzbekistan¹¹. This law, in the early years of independence, provided an important legal framework for the development and implementation of youth-related policies in the country. On the basis of this law, it is aimed at the formation of public policy on young people, the protection of their rights and freedoms, the implementation of effective public policies in education, health, social protection, vocational training, employment and other important areas. It also defined the responsibility of the state on youth issues and strengthened the legal framework for creating conditions for youth development, integration into social life in the country. Youth policy became one of the main directions in the large-scale reforms of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the following years.

In conclusion, the essence of state policy on young people is to educate them as a younger generation that contributes to the development of society, for which they can be listed above.

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¹⁰ Ильинский, И. М. Молодежь и молодежная политика: философия. История. Теория. - М.: Голос, 2001. - 696 с

¹¹ O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Kengashining Axborotnomasi, 1992-y., 2-son, 80-modda; O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Majlisining Axborotnomasi, 1998-y., 5-6-son, 102-modda; O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Qonun hujjatlari to‘plami, 2004-y., 25-son, 287-modda; 51-son, 514-modda; 2008-y., 52-son, 513-modda

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